

ACTIVE AUDIENCE: MEDIA USE FOR SOCIAL GRATIFICATIONS

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Abstract:

Mass society theory and the response to it focused researchers' attention primarily on the unintended, negative consequences of mass media. Audiences were seen as passively responding to whatever content the media made available to them. Much of the empirical research was therefore 'effects research', which assumed that media did things to people, often without their consent or desire. This research tended to focus on negative effects – the 'bad things' that happen to people as a result of using media. In contrast to this perspective, active audience theories do not seek to understand what media do to people, but rather focus on assessing what people do with media. For this reason, these theories are referred to as audience-centered rather than source-dominated theories. This idea, that people use particular media and specific media content in certain ways in the hope of gratifying a particular need or set of needs, forms the basis of the theoretical perspective explored in this paper.

Keywords: active audience; audience-centered theories; interchangeability of the media; social uses of the media; uses and gratifications.

Introduction

The evolution and social-historical role of mass media have been seen by John B. Thompson (1995) in three ways: a) as a 'pillar' of the constitution of modernity and the shaping of the modern world, alongside the processes of secularization and rationalization, whose role has too long been overrated at the expense of recognition of the relationship between the media and the genesis of modernity; b) as the 'miracle' of the twentieth century, when the world is not only 'represented' in the media, but is 'saturated' and 'transfigured' by the

media; c) as a possible 'curse of the twenty-first century', his prediction of the future impact of the media on the world being a pessimistic one.

Over the last decades, however, beyond the study of the social-historical role and functions of the media, research from the perspective of the socio-human sciences, and in particular from the perspective of communication sciences and sociology, has paid particular attention to the place media occupy in people's lives. At a general level, three metaphors can be identified that capture contemporary thinking about media (Meyrowitz, 1993):

- a) Media can be seen as *a conduit* for conveying certain meanings; this is often the metaphor behind public concerns about unwanted or harmful content.
- b) Media can be seen as *a language*; here researchers concerned with technology and text analysis focus on media codes or 'grammar' (Ștefănescu, 2004).
- c) Media can be seen as *an environment*; from this perspective, questions arise about the interactional and relational possibilities of different media, with media seen as shaping the social context for communication as well as their content.

Early audience research

Audience researchers, from the earliest days of such research, have observed and emphasized that media use was shaped by circumstances of time and place, as well as by social and cultural customs and traditions (McQuail, 1997: 88). People became audiences for various social reasons (e.g., for conversation or organizing daily routines), as well as for communicative values and purposes (e.g., finding out what the news was). Eliot Friedson (1953), for example, emphasized the importance of the character of the group to the individual's experience in relation to the media (in contrast to what was proposed by the theory of mass behavior). He argued that contemporary evidence on film and radio audiences was a good basis for this. Most audience behavior, he wrote, takes place in a complex network of local social activities. Certain moments of the day, certain days, certain seasons or months of the year are appropriate times to engage in specific activities connected with different media. The individual is frequently accompanied by others in his or her social

group and participates in an interpersonal network of bystanders who discuss the meanings of past experience with mass communication and anticipate the meaning of future experience.

Early research on media audiences was, however, to a greater or lesser extent, overshadowed by the model of communication understood as a linear process of transmitting 'messages', which privileged the 'content' of the message, as well as its 'impact', understanding the audience as an 'aggregate' of unrelated individuals and treating audience activity as 'exposure' to messages (Ștefănescu, 2009b). The most important thing, from this point of view, was that messages were received consciously, recorded and effective. The characteristics of social life that interfered in any way or 'got in the way' of this linear process were either considered/treated as 'noise', as interference, or as inconveniences meant to irritate the measurement process. 'Unmotivated' behavior was often disregarded as 'meaningless'. The perspective on audiences that accompanied the broadcast model of media was that audiences could best be studied in laboratories (if that were possible), leaving 'irrelevant' aspects out of consideration.

Some paradigm shifts

Today, however, audience researchers know that media use is generally random, untidy, inefficient, a matter of chance and having multiple meanings (Friedson, 1953). Moreover, the term 'audience' itself is ambiguous, as it simultaneously denotes the level of perception of the messages, the target they are aimed at and the group they reach (Vlăduțescu, 2018: 34). Not only is the model of planned transmission of information an abstraction, but the process it represents is the exception rather than the rule for most communication situations (Sorlin, 2002). It is therefore best forgotten as a means of understanding audiences since it does not even reflect the realities of media industry practice. Early forms of media were often developed to correspond to the lifestyles (home, work, or leisure) of particular social groups and to suit the aspirations and attitudes of potential audiences (Martel & McCall, 1964). The daily newspaper, in its content and in its cycle of production and distribution, was designed to fit into the daily routine of the late nineteenth-century urban worker. The weekly family and women's

magazines were designed to be bought and read occasionally in lonely moments at home. The cinema, in its early days, monopolized urban leisure patterns, especially for couples and groups of friends looking for convenient and inexpensive out-of-home entertainment. The activity of 'going to the movies' has almost always been seen more as a social activity than as an opportunity to see particular films (Handel, 1950). It represented a continuation of the 'audience' in the original sense, made for those who went to public social events, usually in the company of others. The occasion had significance beyond any 'message' communicated or any individual gratification gained. Seeing a 'bad movie' could even give the same satisfaction as seeing a 'good movie'. Much the same can be said about listening to the phonograph and radio, and later watching TV, although, unlike cinema, these almost always took a back seat in the complex patterns of family life (McQuail, 1997: 89).

The phrase 'watching TV' is generally a more accurate description of what is happening than the phrase 'watching programs on television', but it also exaggerates the significance of the constantly moving screen. Extensive and detailed studies of time use (Kubey & Csikszentmihalyi, 1990), based on self-reports, leave little doubt about the general non-involvement and secondary nature of TV viewing, although this should not be confused with the meaninglessness of TV viewing (McQuail, 1997: 90).

The casual and arbitrary/random character of media use is in fact only a matter of perception, since there is always a certain logic, but this is usually not the logic of the 'media exposure' model. The transmissionist model and the biases of the behaviorist perspective have tended to distort audience research, as does theory that conceptualizes audiences as a mass of isolated individuals, 'exposed' to external influences (idem).

'Active audience' theories

In contrast to these latter theoretical perspectives, "active audience" theories do not attempt to understand *what media do with people* (as is the case in most 'effects' theories and research), but instead attempt to evaluate *what people do with media*. For this reason, they are

considered audience-centered theories, in contrast to source-centered theories. They are microsocial rather than macrosocial perspectives.

Many of the empirical research is, as mentioned, research of 'effects', that is, it starts from the premise that the media have various consequences on people, often without their consent or desire. Such research often focuses on the negative effects, that is, on the 'bad things' that happen to individuals because they use the media. The effects were seen to have varied causes, from political propaganda to dramatized depictions of sex and violence (Baran & Davis, 2000: 245). The theory of mass society and its subsequent developments have directed researchers' attention almost exclusively to these unintended and negative consequences of mass media. However, there have been early critics of this view. For example, John Dewey (1927) pointed out that educated people can use mass media for good purposes (apud Baran & Davis, 2000: 246). He saw the problem of propaganda as one that could be solved by public education rather than censorship: if people were taught to make better use of mass media content, then there would be no need to be protected from it. But despite such arguments, empirical research focused, at the time, but also later, especially on the delimitation of evidence regarding how ordinary people can be manipulated by the media.

Subsequent research on media effects found that people are not quite as vulnerable to propaganda as mass society theory predicted, because they are 'protected' from manipulation by opinion leaders and especially by the stable and intense attitudes they hold. However, such optimistic conclusions have also been associated with a pessimistic view of the ordinary individual: if the 'barriers that protect them' are broken, then such an individual can be easily manipulated (Baran & Davis, 2000: 246). It is precisely because of these views, that research based on the premise that ordinary individuals can be responsible consumers of the media, has developed very slowly.

During the 1970s and 1980s, cultural and empirical research on media began to focus more on media audiences. Their goal was to better and more usefully understand what people do with media use in their everyday lives. Television use grew exponentially during the 1960s, but very little research had been done to examine what people do when they

watch television (Drăgan, 2007b). Were viewers fundamentally passive consumers of television entertainment, or did watching TV serve more important purposes? As such research was conducted, new and less pessimistic conceptualizations of audiences began to develop. At the same time, scholars focused on cultural studies were discovering, through their research findings, that the power of elites to manipulate audiences was not as great as critical theorists had assumed (Baran & Davis, 2000: 246).

While the audience was initially perceived as an undifferentiated mass, a passive target of information or persuasion efforts, or a market of consumers of media products, researchers interested in media effects have had to recognize, however, especially with the development of television, that real audiences are composed of real social groups, characterized by the existence of networks of interpersonal relationships that mediate the effects of media (McQuail & Windahl, 2004: 107).

Moreover, audiences may resist influence partly because they have different motivations when 'exposing' themselves to media messages. Research has provided evidence supporting the idea of *selective exposure to media messages*, as well as the fact that audiences tend to match their choice of channels and content with their tastes, ideas and information needs. As a result of this process, the media's chances of achieving the change effect decrease and the chances of the consolidation effect increase.

Uses and gratifications theory

The main model that has theorized these ideas and evidence of the existence of active audiences is the *uses and gratifications model*. This model considers *the media consumer* (reader, listener, viewer) as *an active participant* in the communication process. In terms of analyzing the effects or influence of media, this model shows that it is not enough to find out whether people 'exposed themselves' to media, but it is necessary to find out *why* they were exposed to *particular* media messages or products and *what they expected* to gain from that experience.

Unlike the transmissionist or mechanistic model of communication, which considered that there is a linear link between media messages and their effects on individuals (Ștefănescu, 2009b), the "uses and gratifications" model assumes that a variety of elements intervene

between media messages and their effects, such as individual predispositions and the process of selective perception, group norms, dissemination of the message through interpersonal channels, etc. The uses and gratifications model also differs from a previously developed model of communication, namely *the minimal effects model*, in that it does not exclude the possibility of media effects, but with the caveat that a) the media by themselves are usually not sufficient causes for effects on the audience, and b) the media message is only one source of influence, alongside other sources. Media effects are explained, in the 'uses and gratifications' model, "in terms of purposes, functions, and uses controlled by the selection patterns of receivers" (Fisher, 1978: 159).

The basic elements of the uses and gratifications theory are: a) needs and motives for communication, b) the psychological and social environment, c) functional alternatives of media use, d) communication behavior, and e) the consequences of this behavior. The objectives of the model, as seen by its main proponents (see Blumler & Katz, 1974: 19-32), were:

- 1) to explain how people use media to satisfy their own needs;
- 2) to understand the reasons for behavior towards the media;
- 3) to identify the functions or consequences arising from needs, reasons and behavior.

Therefore, the uses and gratifications focus on: a) social and psychological origins of b) needs that generate c) expectations towards d) media and other sources, which lead to e) different patterns of media exposure (or engagement in other activities), resulting in f) the satisfaction of needs and g) other, sometimes unintended, consequences (idem).

The premises of the use and gratifications theory have been also confirmed by more recent research that examined the practice of using new media, such as the internet and mobile phones. For example, a study of teenagers' use of the internet in the 2000s (Ștefănescu, 2009a) highlighted the fact that its use fulfilled the needs of young people related to communication with peers, but also needs for fun, entertainment, information, knowledge, etc., providing gratifications such as a sense of freedom, usefulness, relaxation, being together with others, but also the desired solitude at times, as well as the opportunity to escape from reality (Ștefănescu, 2008a; Ștefănescu, 2008b). Similarly, using the mobile phones in their initial phase, before the appearance of

smartphones, fulfilled needs such as affection, sociability, entertainment, instrumentality, and gratified people with social status, psychological reassurance, and especially immediate access and mobility, as now phoning was possible not only at home, but also in the car, on the bus or train, when visiting, on the street, at work, and so on (Leung & Wei, 2000).

More recently, the use of social media (Leung, 2013; Menon, 2022) seems to fulfill human needs and motivations related to sociality, affection, entertainment, self-seeking, but also the need to vent negative feelings, and to offer gratifications such as recognition, a sense of belonging, as well as the opportunity of a 'public arena' for the exposure of one's personality.

It is not only young people and adults who benefit from using new media, such as the internet, but also older people who, when considering the issue of health for example, use the internet for gaining online health-related information (Rodat, 2021a), but also for communication with loved ones, such as family members (Rodat, 2021b), information in the general sense, and for being aware of current developments, therapies and medication treatments (Marinescu & Rodat, 2018). These media consumers have also the gratification of having more power through the internet, more precisely through forums, as well as through the ratings, evaluations and comments that are now possible through this new medium, for example in relation to doctors, clinics, hospitals and the medical system in general (Rodat, 2021c).

'Interchangeability' of the media and 'using the media for important things'

Starting from the needs and motivations of people's orientation towards certain media, their preferences for one medium or another and the satisfactions offered by different media, the viewpoint of "*the interchangeability of the media*" was simultaneously developed, through which the similarities and differences between the media were expressed and explained. Known also as the *circular media model*, this view was depicted by Katz, Haas, and Gurevitch (1973) in their article "On the use of the mass media for important things". According to their perspective, each medium shows increased similarities with two

'neighboring' media, which means that in the absence of the respective medium, its functions are taken over by one of its neighbors. This was named by the phrase "the interchangeability of the media" (Drăgan, 2007a: 363). For example, at that time, in the 1970s, the place of the functions of books could be taken by those of newspapers or cinema, listening to the radio could be replaced by reading newspapers and watching television, while television was seen as interchangeable with cinema and radio.

The 'interchangeability' of the media over a variety of functions orders media like newspapers, radio, television, books, and cinema in a "circumplex" (Katz et al., 1973: 164). The premise of the circular model is that the media approach each other (are similar) "according to the needs predominantly satisfied and the main gratifications offered" (Drăgan, 2007a: 364), and the various "attributes of the media explain the social and psychological needs they serve best" (Katz et al., 1973: 164). Thus, as the authors of the model point out, newspapers, radio and television are used by people more for contact with reality, while books and movies are used more to get away from reality. More educated people tend to use print media more, while less educated people lean towards audiovisual media. Television is a 'universal' medium, being able to cover the whole range of people's information-communication needs, which makes it the least 'specialized' medium, while books are the medium most used for 'self-knowledge' (Fiske, 2003: 18).

Conclusion

Audience has never been completely absent from mass communication theory, but the 'uses and gratifications' perspective has brought it to a central position in the media approach. The audience-centered perspective synthetically described in this paper, and that emerged as a counter-reaction to both mass society theory and the limited effects paradigm, argues that mass media 'do not do things' to people (this is to be understood in the classical sense of 'effects'), but people 'do things' with mass media (in the sense of 'uses'). This approach to media focuses on the uses to which people put media and the gratifications they seek from those uses (Baran & Davis, 2000: 247).

The basic thesis of this perspective is, therefore, that audiences are active and use the media for the gratification of their own purposes. This idea was, of course, met with resistance and counterarguments. The criticisms were focused both on the conceptual aspects of the model and on the methodological aspects that were the basis of the research that supported it. However, the assertion that audiences are active has proven to be valuable in refining the understanding of the mass communication process. Moreover, it has also had a secondary benefit: it has provided the theoretical basis and fueled interest in scientific approaches to media. In other words, if audiences are central to the process of mass communication, then we must give due importance to their effectiveness in the process.

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